

NIVA WP 3 –SEGES interview

Date: 19 October 2020 - 13h 00 – 14 h 15

Location: Teams meeting

Stakeholder description

1. Organisation name: **SEGES**
2. Person name:
3. Person position /role :
 - Removed for privacy reasons: in charge of relations with farmers and Paying Agencies
 - Removed for privacy reasons : IT specialist and agronomist
4. What is the general purpose of the organisation?

SEGES is a farmer owned professional knowledge and innovation house that works with everything that has to do with farming. From the major agricultural topics in plants, environment, nature conservation, animal husbandry and ecology to economics, tax, law, IT, architecture, accounting, HR and education. This is done in close collaboration with the universities, ministries, companies and interest groups both in Denmark and abroad.

SEGES aims is to build IT products for farmers, SEGES is FMIS editor. Marianne is collecting the rules to be included in the system. SEGES is farmer owned, 90 % of all arable land in DK is in the SEGES database.

5. What are the activities related to agriculture in general ? What are the activities requiring use of data about agriculture?

Look at nr. 4.

In fact, regarding IACS, SEGES is more a data provider than a data user.

User experience – User requirements

1. What current IACS data do you need?

- LPIS data

In Denmark, Reference Parcels and Agricultural Areas are same features. We pick up this data from Paying Agencies at each update cycle. It is useful for farmers in order to make comparisons with agricultural parcels. When a farmer is exploiting a new field, he has to be sure of the limits. In Denmark, for arable lands (what is main part of agricultural lands), there are lots of shifts from one year to the following one => farmers have interest for their neighbour's data.

It is public data in Denmark, we can get it easily. Denmark has a policy of open data: nearly all official data is open.

All SEGES it-products use the official maps e.g. LPIS, streams, wetlands, ponds, historical monuments. Most of this data is not owned by Paying Agencies but comes from other Ministries, it is also open data.

- GSAA data

In practice, our data comes to Paying Agencies and then, once validated, comes back to our database.

- The farmer prepares his/her field plan, during the winter using our FMIS; field and fertilizer planning is mandatory
- The FMIS knows the CAP rules and advice the farmers about what they can declare and provide warnings about optimising these aids
- The data captured in FMIS is then extracted for the GSAA ; the application is uploaded to the PA's application platform in electronic form using xml-file The PA application platform checks the application and the application-field map are corrected if necessary (e.g. cut the geometry that is outside the reference parcel)
- The application is then submitted to the PA
- The corrected field boundaries are sent back to FMIS with its official geometry that can be used by farmer next year for his/her declaration.

Most data from PA is public. Data from SEGES database is stored privately, there is need of farmer authorization to provide it.

From these data, SEGES is making statistics about crops types (e.g. where and how much a specific species of potatoes is cultivated) in order to help farmers to make their field plans.

- Animals

SEGES is running animal database for all farmers. We are doing it for government, it is out of FMIS. Any animal has its data in our database, we have historical information.

- Beneficiaries

We don't store details, just name, contact information (address) and the identifier (tax number).

- Quality controls

Yes, we'd like to have these data but we don't get them. Farmers would be willing to follow development of their dossier; it is currently black box. Making the quality control more open would make farmers feel safer.

- Entitlements

SEGES is hoping that this system will disappear. Paying Agency has data about it; it is open for farmers and their advisers.

- Payments

In FMIS, we try to calculate in advance the payment. We don't have specific interest in the data from Paying Agency. In our point of view, this data should be open just for the concerned farmer (and adviser).

1. What potential future IACS data do you need?

- Farm holding (Farm Registry)

It is already in our database (FMIS) that is main source of this data.

- Crop plots (Farm Registry)

For crop plots, our FMIS will be data provider. There are lots of land that is rented and so interest to find this information.

- Farm plans (Seamless Claim)

Field plans are in our FMIS database.

- Crop classification & Traffic lights (EO monitoring)

There is some implementation of EO monitoring in Denmark. First year (2019), farmers got news about traffic lights quite often (9 times); the second year (2020), this was not so often (3 times).

Farmers can go to the monitoring system and using their identifier, see their fields and the related traffic light. Having news 3 or 4 times per year would be fine. There is big interest.

In addition, SEGES is using satellite images (mainly Sentinel from Sinergise) to monitor fertilizers, seeds, Yields....

- Geotagged photos

The application is already in place in Denmark.

- Farmer performance

Yes, once these indicators have been defined, there will be interest from professional farming. There is a will from farmers to see everything (without the will to give everything).

- Agro-environmental indicators

Yes, all 3 topics are of interest. We have a system of farm monitoring regarding nitrate leaching, farmers have to ask permission, there is a quota regarding nutrient level.

Opinion about data sharing principles

1. What data do you think should be publicly available for use?

Public data; for instance, crop maps are public data.

2. What data do you think should not be shared and should only be used by Paying Agencies?

- What has made you feel this way/why do you think this way?

3. Who do you think most benefits from partially or open data sharing?

- Can you explain why you feel this way?

Journalists (if data totally open) but farmers are not willing to share all their data without specific reason to do so. Data that is provided for Paying Agencies should not be for newspapers.

4. Do you have any idea about how the process of data sharing from farmer to wider stakeholder groups can be improved?

Distinction has to be done between what is public data and what is industrial, business secret. Public data might be records showing that farmers respect regulations (e.g. about pollution) or to get public aids. But farmers are working in competitive environment, they are not willing to provide to everyone how they manage their farms, what can make them better than their neighbours. Looking at other farmers data should be allowed only if specific interest.

To get more data from farmers, it is important to ensure transparency: make clear why data is needed and ensure farmers that their data will be used for this purpose only.

Farmers may be willing to share more data if it helps them to get “good stamp” without having to tell everything: good stamp may be about animal welfare, organic farming, quality. These good stamps may help farmers to sell their production.